

MSE¹ = 0: The Perfect *Error* of Overfitting

A convergence at the boundaries of Mathematics, Artificial Intelligence, and Epistemology
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SUMMARY

Why does memorising past-paper questions not guarantee success in exams? Why does ChatGPT not memorise the content of the entire internet? Both questions have the same answer: overfitting—the trap of adapting to existing data so precisely, that the advantages of generalisation are lost.

This article introduces overfitting through an example based on predicting daily temperatures. It then develops the underlying mathematics—mean squared error, the Lagrange interpolation theorem, and the bias–variance tradeoff framework. Next, it links overfitting to the training of large language models (LLMs) and argues that algorithmic overfitting in social media can produce “certainty” without scientific truth.

Finally, it connects overfitting to the ideas of Popper, Kolmogorov, Kahneman, Descartes, and Aristotle through the core concepts of the ‘first principles’ and generalisation.

This is an expository article rather than a research paper. It is aimed primarily at high school students interested in mathematics. The approach is interdisciplinary, synthesising ideas from mathematics, artificial intelligence (AI), and epistemology (theory of knowledge).

KEY WORDS

overfitting, mean squared error, Lagrange interpolation theorem, large language model, LLM, first principles, mathematical generalisation, artificial intelligence, AI, test set, training set.

CENTRAL QUESTION

Under what mathematical conditions does a computational model fail to generalise what it has learned? What is the fundamental principle that distinguishes superficial adaptation to data from true *understanding*, both in mathematical modelling and in AI systems?

INTRODUCTION - After the exam

“How is it possible that I did so badly?” Alex could not believe it. Although he had studied for endless hours, he ended up performing poorly in the exam. Usually before each test, he only studies past-paper questions and memorises the answers to perfection. When questions very similar to the ones he has studied appear, he is unstoppable. But when the questions are even slightly different (and they usually are), he gets stuck.

Figure 1: Overfitting a doghouse.

On the other hand, we have his classmate, Jane. She studies for half as long and does significantly fewer practice problems than Alex. However, when she encounters a question, she tries to understand **why** the method works. She does not memorise the material; she tries to understand it in depth.

In practice sessions, Alex often scores higher, but in real exams Jane surpasses him. The difference between them is not effort; it is a concept that mathematicians and computer scientists call **overfitting** – one of the most important ideas in modern AI. [1]

Mathematically speaking, Alex achieves near-zero error on his **training set**, (past papers), but high error in the **test set** (new exam questions). On the contrary, Jane performs less well in the training set, but much better in the test set. Alex has **memorised**; Jane has **generalized**. The distinction between the two meanings is the main subject of this article.

The next four chapters present an example with simulated daily temperature data to make the mathematics easier to follow.

¹ MSE is the Mean Square Error

THREE MATHEMATICAL MODELS - Temperature changes

Suppose a meteorologist measures the air temperature 13 times during a 24-hour period. The goal is to find a mathematical model that fits these measurements closely, so the meteorologist can estimate temperatures at unmeasured times.

The mathematical model² will be an **nth degree polynomial** of the form:

$$P(x) = a_n x^n + a_{n-1} x^{n-1} + a_{n-2} x^{n-2} + \dots + a_2 x^2 + a_1 x + a_0 \quad (1)$$

In equation (1), $P(x)$ is the predicted temperature, x is the input variable (time in hours), and the coefficients a_0, a_1, \dots, a_n are constants chosen so that the curve fits the input data as closely as possible. [3]

For example, a_0 shifts the whole curve up or down, a_1 controls the slope, a_2 controls the curvature (convex vs concave), and higher order coefficients add progressively finer local variation.

Estimating these coefficients is, in effect, **training the model**.

The **Least-Squares Method**³ (LSM) explained in the next chapter, provides a reliable option to evaluate the model, since it minimises the sum of squared errors (the differences) between the observed values and the model's predictions.

The meteorologist tests three models, as shown in *Figure 2*. [2]

- **1st degree polynomial**: It is a straight line that does not reflect temperature changes. It is a good example of **underfitting**, the opposite of overfitting. It is obvious that it cannot sufficiently represent the wave-like pattern of temperature.
- **3rd degree polynomial**: A cubic curve with local maxima and minima, which renders the curve-like change in temperature quite well.
- **12th degree polynomial**: The graph of the polynomial passes through every single measurement point. It should be the most appropriate graph overall, but it is not. We observe strongly curved outbursts between points that predict absurd temperatures, such as near 01:00h⁴. When used to predict temperatures outside of the measurement hours, it collapses. This is a good example of **overfitting**.

Figure 2: Three polynomials fitted to the same 13 temperature measurements. Identical input data, different results.

At this point it is worth noting that *underfitted* models fail everywhere and always, but their error is **predictable**; we know that the model is unsatisfactory. *Overfitted* models can deceive us. They look perfect on known data yet collapse on unseen data – their failure is **unpredictable**. [3, 4, 5]

Put simply, *underfitting* is a case of **known unknowns** – we know what we don't know. *Overfitting* is a case of **unknown unknowns** – we don't know that we don't know.

² In this article, the terms "model" and "polynomial" are used interchangeably, referring specifically to the polynomial interpolation model.

³ The LSM was developed independently by two leading mathematicians in the early 19th century. Adrien-Marie Legendre published it first (1805), while **Carl Friedrich Gauss** later claimed to have developed it as early as 1795, and published it in 1809 in his work "Theoria motus corporum coelestium".

⁴ High-degree Lagrange interpolation polynomials can exhibit large oscillations (errors), especially near the edges of the interval. Carl Runge identified this phenomenon (1901) by studying the function: $f(x) = \frac{1}{1+25x^2}$ in the space $[-1, 1]$. The Runge effect is a classic problem in Numerical Analysis that can occur when approximating a function using high-degree polynomial interpolation.

HOW WRONG IS WRONG - Lagrange Interpolation & MSE

To quantify how well each model fits the data, we can use the **Mean Squared Error (MSE)**. For a dataset with n measurements y_i , and corresponding model predictions \hat{y}_i , the MSE is:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (2)$$

Each term $(y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$ is a squared residual – the squared difference between the actual measurement and the prediction (see *Figure 3*).

There are two reasons we square the difference. The first is that squaring removes the sign so positive and negative errors do not cancel each other out. The second reason is that squaring gives more weight to large errors, effectively “*penalising*” the predictions that deviate strongly from the measurements. With this method we can improve the polynomial fit under additional constraints.

Figure 3 shows the MSE for the 3rd degree polynomial.

Figure 3: Squared residuals for the 3rd degree polynomial. Each square has an area equal to the error square at the point. MSE is their average.

But what about the 12th degree polynomial?

As already explained, the 12th degree polynomial has $MSE = 0$. Every squared residual is 0. This is not a coincidence; it is a mathematical certainty, since the polynomial was constructed to pass through every measurement point.

In 1795, the Italian-French mathematician Joseph-Louis Lagrange formulated the **Lagrange Interpolation Theorem**, one of the key theorems in Numerical Analysis. It states that for any n data points, there exists a unique polynomial of $n - 1$ degree that passes through all of them; that is, it satisfies the condition: $L(x_i) = y_i$ for every $i = 1, \dots, n$.

Figure 4: J.L. Lagrange (1736-1813)

In our example, with 13 measurement points, the 12th degree polynomial has 13 coefficients (one for each point). These coefficients can be chosen so that the curve passes exactly through all 13 points, giving $MSE = 0$. According to Lagrange, for every data point i , we define a **Base Polynomial**⁵:

$$\ell_i(x) = \prod_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^n \frac{x - x_j}{x_i - x_j} \quad (3)^6$$

The base polynomial has the following property:

⁵ In equation (3), the numerator is the product $(x-x_1)(x-x_2)\dots(x-x_n)$, excluding the factor $(x-x_i)$. Therefore, the numerator is zero at every point $x=x_j$, with $j \neq i$. The denominator is the same product as the numerator, but with x replaced by x_i . That is the numerator evaluated at $x=x_i$. This ensures that at point x_i the result will be 1.

⁶ The uppercase **Π** in mathematics is the product symbol. It is used to represent the product of a sequence of terms.

Evaluating at $x=x_i$, gives $\ell_i(x_i) = 1$. If we substitute any other x_j (where $j \neq i$), then $\ell_i(x_j) = 0$.

The final interpolation polynomial is the sum of the base polynomials, each multiplied by the corresponding y_i .

$$L(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n y_i \ell_i(x) \quad (4)$$

Lagrange's interpolation polynomial would produce $MSE = 0$ for any set of 13 temperature values. It does this without indicating whether the data contains any meaningful pattern, simply solving 13 equations with 13 unknowns. Therefore, the 12th degree polynomial has merely "**memorised**" every measurement. Its predictive value is essentially none.

TRAINING THE MATHEMATICAL MODEL

So far, we have seen that in the temperature example, the 1st degree and 12th degree polynomials have essentially no predictive value, whereas the 3rd degree polynomial is quite suitable. This naturally raises a series of questions:

- Would a 4th or 5th degree polynomial work better?
- Which polynomial degree minimises the MSE while also producing the best-trained (best-generalising) model?

To answer the questions above, we need to test the model on new data that it has not seen before. To do this, we split the dataset into two subsets: the **training set** and the **test set**. From our 13 temperature measurements we use 10 of them (about 80%) for training, and the remaining 3 for testing. [5, 6]

We can now calculate two separate error measures, one on the training set and one on the test set: MSE_{train} vs. MSE_{test} . Figure 5 shows the MSEs for the two subsets as we increase the polynomial degree from 1 to 10. From the blue line (MSE_{train}), we see that as the model gains more parameters, the training MSE decreases; by the 10th degree polynomial it is almost zero ($MSE_{train} \approx 0$).

Figure 5: As the polynomial degree increases, MSE_{train} steadily decreases (blue line). In contrast, MSE_{test} reaches a minimum and then begins to rise (red line).

In contrast, the red line (MSE_{test}) behaves differently. At low polynomial degrees, MSE_{test} is very high. As the polynomial degree increases, MSE_{test} decreases and reaches its minimum at degree 4 (or 5). However, beyond that point, further increases in degree cause MSE_{test} to rise again. This pattern is typical of *overfitting*.

In our example, for 8th degree polynomials and higher: $MSE_{train} \approx 0$ but $MSE_{test} \gg 0$ (5)⁷

In conclusion, our example shows that a model with $MSE_{train} = 0$ has likely **memorised** the training data, whereas a model with a low MSE_{test} has **learned** a pattern and therefore has predictive value.

⁷ \approx means: approximately equal to. \gg means much greater than.

BIAS & VARIANCE - Why models fail

When a model goes wrong, it usually happens for one of two reasons that pull in opposite directions: **bias** (too simple) or **variance** (too sensitive).

Bias happens when a model is too simple. Look at the 1st degree polynomial (the straight line) in *Figure 2*. It assumes temperature changes linearly, but the real temperatures follow a curve. So even with more data, a straight line cannot capture the real pattern. Bias measures the difference between the model's average **expected** prediction and the true value:

$$\text{Bias}^2 = (\bar{\hat{y}} - y)^2 \quad (6)$$

Here, $\bar{\hat{y}}$ is the model's average expected prediction across many different *training sets*, and y is the true (noise-free) value at that x . A model with high bias tends to make the **same type of error consistently**. This is called **underfitting**.

Variance, on the other hand, is the opposite problem. It results from a very "sensitive" model, such as the 12th degree polynomial in *Figure 2*. Because the model tries to pass through every data point, small changes in the measurements can produce large changes in the fitted curve. If we repeated the experiment on a different day, with slightly different temperature readings, the 1st degree line would barely change at all, whereas the 12th degree curve could look completely different. Variance measures exactly this instability: the tendency of the fitted curve to change dramatically in response to small fluctuations in the data.

$$\text{Variance} = \mathbb{E}[(\hat{y} - \bar{\hat{y}})^2] \quad (7)^8$$

A model with high variance does not make consistent / systematic errors; instead, its errors are **unpredictable**. This is called **overfitting**. These two types of errors are linked by an identity that expresses the model's total prediction error as follows:

$$\text{Total Error} = \text{Bias}^2 + \text{Variance} + \text{Noise} \quad (8)^9$$

In **machine-learning** bibliography, equation (8) is the *bias-variance decomposition*, which underlies the **bias-variance trade-off**. The proof of equation (8) is given in the Appendix to avoid interrupting the main discussion. [7, 8]

The graphical illustration of this equation is shown in *Figure 6*. As the polynomial degree increases, *bias* decreases and tends toward zero, while *variance* increases rapidly. The total error forms a U-shaped curve, where its minimum indicates the preferred polynomial degree.

The bias-variance decomposition helps explain the bias-variance trade-off: in many learning problems, reducing bias (often by using a more flexible model) tends to increase variance, and reducing variance tends to increase bias. In real data there is also irreducible noise, which sets a lower bound on the achievable prediction error - so zero total error is generally impossible.

Figure 6: Bias - Variance Tradeoff. The two categories of errors are presented along with the total error and the sweet spot which practically shows the ideal polynomial degree of the model (see also Figure 5).

⁸ The symbol \mathbb{E} denotes the **expected value** (mathematical expectation), i.e., the average over many repetitions. Here it refers to the model's average prediction across many training sets and is used to quantify how sensitive the model is to small changes in the data.

⁹ Noise refers to **Irreducible Noise**: the part of the error that no model can eliminate. In our example, even the most accurate model cannot predict the exact temperature, because unpredictable factors -such as the shadow of a cloud- may affect it at random. In other words, irreducible noise sets the **lower bound** on the error of any prediction.

LLMs - Patterns, Not Copies

Large language models don't store the entire internet verbatim; they **do not memorise**. Instead, they learn statistical patterns from huge amounts of text—much like our polynomial models either capture the overall shape of the temperature curve or overfit individual points. In this chapter, we connect that idea of *generalisation vs overfitting* to what LLMs actually learn during training.

ChatGPT 3 had about 175 billion parameters. Very simplistically, we can think of these parameters as the “coefficients” of our earlier polynomial model¹⁰. Its training data was about 300 billion **tokens**¹¹. AI models do not work like *search engines* retrieving memorised text. Instead, training adjusts the parameters, so the model captures the statistical structure of the language—for example, common word sequences, ideas typically appear together, etc. In other words, the parameters do not contain the exact sentences from the internet, but they encode the patterns, to be able to generate new sentences. It is the same process Jane used; instead to memorise past paper questions she learns the logic behind them. [8]

However, a model with so many parameters can **overfit**. To reduce overfitting, ChatGPT's engineers and mathematicians used three tools:

- **Regularisation:** During training, the model is “penalised” not only for prediction errors but also for becoming too dependent on specific patterns. In simple terms, it is like a teacher who says, “*You will lose points if your essay exceeds 500 words.*” This forces the student to focus on the essence of the answer instead of repeating memorised material.
- **Test set** (also called validation set): Generalisation is monitored during training using data the model has not trained on. If MSE_{train} keeps decreasing while MSE_{test} starts increasing, overfitting has begun.
- **Early stopping:** Training is stopped when MSE_{test} reaches its minimum value.

Entropy¹², Signal and Noise – What LLMs actually Learn

Entropy is a concept from physics that the American mathematician **Claude Shannon** borrowed to describe how unpredictable a message is, in his seminal work in information theory titled “*A Mathematical Theory of Communication* (1948)”. Shannon distinguished the **signal**—the meaningful information you want to convey—from **noise**, i.e. random fluctuations that carry no meaning. An overfitted model fails to make this distinction: it treats noise as if it were signal and gives it the same importance. [11]

This idea connects directly to LLMs. ChatGPT is trained to find the **low-entropy structure** in data—that is, the deeper, repeatable patterns of language across hundreds of billions of words. If it overfits, it also learns the noise: random, non-repeating details. As a result, it can lose its ability to generalise.

Overfitting & Context Drift - A Hidden Failure Mode of LLMs

There is a lesser-known form of *overfitting* that can occur when we use LLMs in long chats. These models do not remember what has been mentioned in the human sense; instead, they generate each new answer by reading the conversation history (the *context*) again. When a chat becomes too long, three things can happen:

- First, the earliest messages and instructions receive less attention and may be effectively “forgotten.”
- Second, if the model makes a mistake halfway through the conversation, that mistake becomes part of the context and can influence later answers—so the model can literally **overfit the conversation's noise**.
- Third, the model gradually adapts to the most recent part of the chat and loses the “big picture.” This is called **context drift**.

What is the solution? Start a new chat for each new section, repeat the key instructions, and evaluate the answers critically. In this case, **the “test set” is the user's own judgement**.

¹⁰ LLMs do not use polynomials - this is a simplification. LLMs are based on **Linear Algebra**: their parameters being elements of multi-dimensional weight matrices. Each token becomes a vector of hundreds or thousands of dimensions. Training optimises thousands of matrices through multiplication and transformation operations. Overfitting means these weight-matrices become overly adapted to the training data, losing generalisation ability — just like the 12th degree polynomial.

¹¹ A Token is the basic unit of text that a language model processes. It may be a character, part of a word, or a whole word. On average, one token corresponds to about three-quarters of an English word.

¹² Entropy, although Shannon borrowed the term from Physics, measures the **average uncertainty** of an information source. The more unpredictable the message, the higher its entropy. For example, if you can almost perfectly predict what someone is going to say, the message has **low entropy**, i.e. little new information. If you cannot predict it at all, it has **high entropy** and carries more information.

A MODEL THAT EXPLAINS EVERYTHING, HAS UNDERSTOOD NOTHING

Figure 7: Karl Popper (1902-1994)

In the 14th century, **William of Ockham** argued that "*when two explanations fit the same data equally well, we should prefer the simplest one, the one that has the fewest assumptions.*" This principle is known as **Occam's razor**, which 'shaves' away all the unnecessary details and assumptions from a theory.

In 1934, Philosopher **Karl Popper** argued that a good theory is not the one that explains everything, instead, it is the one that **forbids** something. Put simply, a theory compatible with every observation risk nothing, commits to nothing, and teaches us nothing. He called this principle **falsifiability**: a theory gains scientific credibility by making predictions, that could potentially be proven wrong — if they are wrong. The 12th degree polynomial of our example perfectly fits any 13 data points by construction; it can never be wrong. It is **irrefutable**. [9]

Figure 8: Andrey Kolmogorov (1903-1987)

In the 1960s, mathematician **Andrey Kolmogorov** — one of the founders of the *Algorithmic Information Theory* posed a seemingly simple question: "*Is there an objective way to measure how complex a dataset is?*" His elegant answer defined the complexity of a dataset as the length of the **shortest program** that can produce it. Applied to our example, the daily temperature follows a simple sinusoidal pattern described by just a few parameters. In contrast, reproducing the 12th degree polynomial requires all 13 coefficients — a seemingly random list with high Kolmogorov complexity. [10]

The famous psychologist **Daniel Kahneman**, winner of the 2002 Nobel Prize in Economics, showed that human judgment suffers from the same problems that our article explores. In his landmark book *Thinking Fast and Slow* (2011), he distinguishes two modes of thinking: **System 1**, which is fast and intuitive — essentially a high-variance model that overfits to immediate patterns and calls it "instinct", and **System**

2, which is slow, analytical and deliberate, applying careful reasoning to regulate System's 1 impulsive reactions. [12]

At this point it is reasonable to ask: what connects an English monk of the Middle Ages, an Austrian philosopher, a Soviet mathematician and an Israeli psychologist? None of them wrote a single line of code, none of them fitted polynomials to temperature measurements and none of them ever trained neural networks¹³. And yet, each one working independently, in his own field and era, arrived at the same fundamental insight.

4 thinkers, 7 centuries, 1 idea: **A model that explains everything, has understood nothing.**

OVERFITTING BEYOND THE MACHINE – Certainty without Truth

So far, we have discussed *overfitting* in polynomial and neural networks. But the same trap — the mismanaged bias-variance trade-off — occurs all around us. Let's examine what happens when algorithms and models are designed in ways that **intentionally** lead to overfitting.

Conspiracy theories

Imagine someone who believes the Earth is flat. You show them photos from space missions. They respond: "*the photos are fake, NASA staged them*". You present mathematical proofs. "*The maths is simply wrong*". You point to the curved horizon visible from a ship at sea. "*That's a visual illusion.*"

Their mental model has enormous *Variance* — so much flexibility that it can incorporate any contradictory evidence as just another parameter to explain away. Each new piece of opposing data gets absorbed as an extra variable in their ever-expanding conspiracy. They begin with a simple narrative — a low-degree polynomial. When **contradictory evidence** appears, instead of rejecting the theory, **they add new parameters** to the polynomial, new "culprits", new layers of the conspiracy. The polynomial degree keeps rising, and of course they do not care that their model has become irrefutable according to *Popper* and therefore scientifically

¹³ Artificial neural networks are machine learning computational models, inspired by the structure of the human brain. They consist of interconnected nodes (artificial neurons), and process data to solve complex problems such as, pattern recognition, learning to improve their performance through experience.

useless. They cannot grasp that genuine scientific explanation has low *Kolmogorov complexity*: it is an elegantly simple and short program: "*the Earth is spherical because gravity acts isotropically*".

Social media - Algorithmic myopia - The algorithm as an overfitting machine

The algorithms behind *TikTok*, *YouTube* and *Instagram* are trained to maximize user engagement — this is their *training set*, their measure of success. But the *test set* — the long-term wellbeing of users and the quality of public discourse — is never evaluated. The result is both high variance and high bias. **High variance** because the algorithm overfits excessively to each user's momentary preferences, creating personalised **echo chambers** that amplify fleeting interests. **High bias** because users receive only content that confirms their existing views, systematically excluding opposing perspectives and reducing the rich complexity of human discourse to narrow, predictable streams and reels. Like Alex, who only revises past papers, the algorithm stops presenting you with new information. It only shows you what it has already learned to predict you'll engage with. The result: **Your world becomes smaller and more certain.**

The connection to Kahneman is clear: these algorithms exclusively feed System 1—our fast, emotional, high-variance thinking mode—while systematically bypassing System 2, the slow, deliberate reasoning that normally regulates our impulses. **By design**, they exploit our most reactive mental processes while starving the analytical thinking that might question what we're seeing.

Overfitting isn't just a math and computer science problem; it's how the modern world produces **certainty without truth**, trusting only the feedback *training set*.

CONCLUSION: *αἱ ἀρχαί*¹⁴

We started with Alex and Jane. Alex memorised only past papers and achieved a perfect score on practice tests. Jane understood the underlying principles, made more mistakes in mock exams, but won in the real test. The meteorologist then, tested various models against his temperature data. Lagrange's polynomial guaranteed him $MSE = 0$, but *bias* and *variance* showed him this was not the solution.

Ockham, Popper, Kolmogorov and Kahneman all reached a similar conclusion: perfect adaptation to existing data is not understanding—it is the absence of understanding.

These thinkers described the trap of overfitting from different perspectives, but it was the French philosopher **René Descartes** who, in his *Discours de la méthode* (1637), proposed that we question everything until we reach **irreducible first principles**, and only from there build upwards. Rather than asking '*When is a model too complex?*', Descartes asked: '*What is the absolute minimum from which we should start?*' [13]

The *first principles* inevitably lead us back to ancient Greece, to the **greatest thinker of all** — the one who first formulated all these ideas with the crystal clarity and the mathematical economy of the ancient Greek language:

«ἡ δι' ἐλαττόνων ἄρα κρείττων, εἴπερ ὁμοίως γνώριμοι αἱ ἀρχαί.»

“Proof by fewer principles is superior, if those principles are known.”

Aristotle, *Αναλυτικὰ Ὑστερα*, 350 B.C. [14]

The world is noisy. The real question is not whether our model is perfect; it is whether it has learned something true and useful. The answer mathematicians call **generalization**.

Aristotle called it **wisdom**.

¹⁴ The principles.

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APPENDIX – Mathematical foundation of the Bias - Variance decomposition

Theorem: $Total\ Error = Variance + Bias^2 + Irreducible\ Noise$

$$Total\ Error = \underbrace{\mathbb{E}[(\hat{y} - \bar{y})^2]}_{Variance} + \underbrace{(\bar{y} - f(x))^2}_{Bias^2} + \underbrace{\sigma^2}_{Irreducible\ Noise}$$

Definitions: Suppose $f(x)$ the unknown function we want to approximate and \hat{y} the prediction of our model.

Each observation y contains irreducible noise ε : $y = f(x) + \varepsilon$, where $\mathbb{E}[\varepsilon] = 0$ (the noise is random with zero mean) and $\mathbb{E}[\varepsilon^2] = \sigma^2$ (constant noise variance).

We also define: $\bar{y} = \mathbb{E}[\hat{y}]$, as the mean prediction of the model across many different training sets.

Proof: We start from the definition of Variance: $=\mathbb{E}[(\hat{y} - y)^2]$. We substitute $y = f(x) + \varepsilon$: $=\mathbb{E}[(\hat{y} - f(x) - \varepsilon)^2]$.

We add and subtract \bar{y} to separate the terms: $=\mathbb{E}\left[\left((\hat{y} - \bar{y}) + (\bar{y} - f(x)) - \varepsilon\right)^2\right]$

We briefly define:

- $A = \hat{y} - \bar{y}$: deviation of prediction from its mean
- $B = \bar{y} - f(x)$: mean deviation from the true value
- $C = \varepsilon$: irreducible noise

So: $Total\ Error = \mathbb{E}[(A + B - C)^2]$

We expand: $=\mathbb{E}[A^2] + \mathbb{E}[B^2] + \mathbb{E}[C^2] + 2\mathbb{E}[AB] - 2\mathbb{E}[AC] - 2\mathbb{E}[BC]$

We apply the properties of mathematical expectation:

- $\mathbb{E}[A] = \mathbb{E}[\hat{y} - \bar{y}] = 0$, so, the term $2\mathbb{E}[AB]$ vanishes
- $\mathbb{E}[C] = \mathbb{E}[\varepsilon] = 0$, so, the term $2\mathbb{E}[BC]$ vanishes
- $\mathbb{E}[AC] = \mathbb{E}[(\hat{y} - \bar{y})\varepsilon] = 0$, since noise is independent of the model, the term $2\mathbb{E}[AC]$ vanishes
- $B^2 = (\bar{y} - f(x))^2$ is constant, therefore $\mathbb{E}[B^2] = B^2$

We have three remaining terms: $Total\ Error = \underbrace{\mathbb{E}[(\hat{y} - \bar{y})^2]}_{Variance} + \underbrace{(\bar{y} - f(x))^2}_{Bias^2} + \underbrace{\sigma^2}_{Irreducible\ Noise}$

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] Malato, G. (2021). *An example of overfitting and how to avoid it*.
- [2] Your Data Teacher Blog. Retrieved April 2026, from <https://www.yourdatateacher.com/2021/04/12/an-example-of-overfitting-and-how-to-avoid-it/>
- [3] Hastie, T., Tibshirani, R. & Friedman, J. (2009). *The Elements of Statistical Learning* (2nd ed.). Springer.
- [4] James, G., Witten, D., Hastie, T. & Tibshirani, R. (2013). *An Introduction to Statistical Learning*. Springer.
- [5] Ghojogh, B. & Crowley, M. (2023). The Theory Behind Overfitting, Cross Validation, Regularization, Bagging, and Boosting. *arXiv:1905.12787v2*.
- [6] Stat 20 — Introduction to Probability and Statistics (2025). *Overfitting*. University of California, Berkeley. Retrieved April 2026, from <https://stat20.berkeley.edu/fall-2025/5-prediction/03-overfitting/tutorial.html>
- [7] Bishop, C.M. (2006). *Pattern Recognition and Machine Learning*. Springer.
- [8] Goodfellow, I., Bengio, Y. & Courville, A. (2016). *Deep Learning*. MIT Press.
- [9] Popper, K. (1959). *The Logic of Scientific Discovery*. Hutchinson.
- [10] Kolmogorov, A.N. (1965). *Three approaches to the quantitative definition of information*. Problems of Information Transmission, 1(1), 1-7.
- [11] Shannon, C.E. (1948). *A Mathematical Theory of Communication*. *Bell System Technical Journal*, 27(3), 379–423.
- [12] Kahneman, D. (2011). *Thinking, Fast and Slow*. Farrar, Straus and Giroux.
- [13] Descartes, R. (1637). *Discours de la Méthode*. Leiden: Jan Maire. *Αγγλική μετάφραση: Discourse on the Method (1968)*. Μετάφραση F.E. Sutcliffe. London: Penguin Classics.
- [14] Aristotle (350 BC). *Posterior Analytics*. Book I, Chapter 25, 86a.